

1 **A MULTI-DIMENSIONAL ANALYSIS OF HARD SHOULDER RUNNING**
2 **SYSTEMS**

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1 INTRODUCTION

2 Managed lanes (ML) systems have been operating mainly in Europe and North America as a
3 traffic control strategy that mitigates congestion or adapts traffic conditions to the demand level,
4 by temporarily increasing the physical capacity in freeways and highways. Whilst the
5 implementations vary in composition and performance and the policy is not widely implemented,
6 empirical results ensuing from the existing systems indicated positive impact on network
7 operation. Namely, reduced travel times, improved flow and fewer environmental effects have
8 been experienced, in addition to the less invasive and costly approach of widening constructions.
9 Nevertheless, traffic behavior alterations in the general purpose (GP) lanes that operate in parallel
10 to ML systems are experienced across all facilities. Methods for mitigating the effect of ML
11 systems in capacity, which degrades the initial purpose of the infrastructure, are studied in the
12 current research.

13 In this paper, the authors extend the research that began by Samoili et al. (1). Samoili et
14 al. developed short-term Left Lane Flow Distribution Ratio (LLFDR) models using data from a
15 Managed Lane system equipped freeway in Switzerland. In this paper the authors attempt to cover
16 the questions that have been raised since the initial analysis. First, a segmented analysis of the
17 traffic data is presented and LLFDR prediction models are estimated for the different segments.
18 The results of the presented methodology are compared with the findings of (1). Second, ordered
19 probit models for the satisfaction of the freeway users are estimated, using data that have been
20 collected by 584 paper questionnaires. An economic evaluation of the managed lane system is
21 then performed, to assess the benefits or losses since the beginning of its operation.

22 The paper is structured as follows. The next section describes managed-lane systems
23 around the world and provides a literature review. Subsequently, the segmented analysis, the
24 estimated LLFDR models, and then the behavioral model estimation are introduced. In the last
25 methodological part an economic evaluation of the hard shoulder running system is presented,
26 followed by conclusions and recommendations for future research.

27 STATE OF RESEARCH

28 Managed Lanes Operation Applications

29 The ML systems are utilized aiming to improve mobility, facilitate performance operations,
30 enhance safety and reduce emissions. Sections of each site are reserved, equipped and signed
31 accordingly, allowing the temporary (peak period use) or not circulation of certain or every type
32 of vehicle. In the French city Grenoble, a shoulder lane is open to public transport when the
33 motorway is saturated (2). Similar implementations (Bus Bypass Shoulders (BBS) exist in U.S. in
34 San Diego California, Ontario (Highway 403), New Jersey (Route 9) and Minneapolis-St.Paul
35 region of Minnesota, where reconstructed hard shoulder lanes serve as bus lanes and accidents
36 lanes during peak hours or the whole day.

37 In Paris France, recurrent saturated conditions led in 2005 to the use of shoulder lane as a
38 GP lane during morning and evening peak hours in a three-lane motorway (A4) and a two-lane
39 motorway (2, 3). The system assessment indicated travel time decrease, mainly during morning
40 peak hours.

41 Hard shoulder running (HSR) is also recently employed with improved travel times in
42 Birmingham, England in motorway M42 J3A-7 (4, 5). Precisely, Sultan et al. (4) studied the
43 effect of two speed limits enforcement (50 and 60 mph) upon the temporary hard shoulder use,
44

1 concluding that the higher speed limit provides a reduced travel time of 8%, while there was no
2 evidence of flow increase. A remarkable travel time delay of 65% and capacity increase of 7-22%
3 was observed in a HSR system that was implemented in Netherlands, in order to ease traffic
4 stream mobility (6, 7, 8). The limited underutilization of the shoulder lane shortly after the
5 activation of the system was not considered significant. In Frankfurt (Hesse) Germany, there are
6 also positive results from the scheme in highways A3 and A5, as in a three-lanes section capacity
7 increased up to 25% while HSR, in addition to the safety levels maintenance (9, 10, 11). Another
8 hard shoulder policy is also active in Göttingen, Germany, where a borderline decrease of
9 accidents was denoted when static HSR system with fixed activation time was applied. However,
10 unsteady driving maneuvers were detected, due to confusing lane markings, indicating the impact
11 of the policy to driving behavior.

12 Further indications of traffic behavioral adaptation following the temporal MLs activation
13 are noted in several studies. The authors acknowledge that the presence of different pavement
14 markings to denote the existence of the HSR scheme, the narrower lanes and the enforcement of
15 reduced speed limits, create alterations at the traffic characteristics of the GP lanes and
16 interactions between the latter and the MLs, which lead to an occurrence of different capacity
17 levels between HSR and physical widening of the infrastructure with a GP lane construction (12,
18 13, 14, 15). However, HSR has emerged as aspiring concept of Active Traffic Management (15).

20 DATA DESCRIPTION

22 Traffic Data

23 The study site is a single ML per direction in a two-lane Swiss freeway between Geneva and
24 Lausanne (A1), separated from the GP lanes with pavement signalization. Recurrent congestion
25 emergence and traffic demand increase during peak hours (average daily traffic $Q=82,000$
26 veh/day in both directions), led to the implementation of the facility in 2010. For the ML system
27 implementation, the hard shoulder was broadened and the GP lanes were reduced, resulting in
28 3.50 m of width for every lane. The system is additionally equipped with a partially automated
29 variable speed limit (VSL) policy, which is ensuring the maintenance of security levels. During
30 the ML system operation of the emergency lane as temporary additional lane, a speed
31 harmonization is imposing a 100km/h speed limit, as opposed to the 120 km/h during non-
32 operation. The system was designed to operate based on speed and density thresholds, however it
33 serves as decision support tool, as the traffic control center operators weigh upon its actual
34 activation.

35 The traffic data used for this research (courtesy of SMETRA) have been collected by
36 seven radar sensors on beams located approximately every 500 meters across the freeway. These
37 sensors measure the traffic volume per lane, speed, percentage of heavy vehicles and indications
38 of the opening and closure of the shoulder lane. For the purpose of this research, the data were
39 aggregated per $\Delta t=3\text{min}$ intervals, so as not to interfere to the expression of the traffic dynamics,
40 given the distance between the detectors and the size of the study area.

42 Survey Design and Behavioral Data Collection

43 A survey was designed so as to collect the behavioral data required for the analysis. The design of
44 the questionnaire was based on three aspects: a) limited survey duration, as the survey is
45 conducted during brief stops for refueling or shopping; b) the multi-lingual public that it is

1 addressed to, because of the location of the study area and c) the a priori hypotheses on the factors
2 that could potentially determine users' satisfaction.

3 The structure of the questionnaire was the following: the first section included
4 demographic characteristics that could be observed by the interviewer (gender, age) and survey
5 time, and direct questions regarding the 1) use – or not – of the system while it is activated, 2)
6 inconvenience due to the white continuous line that delineates the emergency lane, 3) frequency
7 of use of the system, 4) traffic conditions amelioration during the hard shoulder running, 5)
8 perceived safety and 6) satisfaction assessment since the system's implementation, and 7) origin
9 region of respondent.

10 Respondents were asked to rate based on a five-level rank, Likert-type scale (16), where
11 "1" corresponds to "not at all" and "5" to "very strongly". The survey was conducted by five
12 interviewers in two sites; the parking lot of a shopping center (local users) and the gas station of
13 the freeway's rest area (mainly traveling users). In order to capture commuter and leisure traffic,
14 the survey period was one working day (Thursday) and one weekend day (Saturday). Taking into
15 consideration the operation of the system, an interval of four hours was opted for, aiming to reveal
16 the trends before and after its activation.

17 18 **METHODOLOGY**

19 To explore a potential amelioration of the operation of an HSR system a multidimensional
20 analysis is performed. The addressed aspects are traffic, behavioral and economic. For the traffic
21 scope, piecewise/segmented linear models are developed. The resulted breakpoint of the
22 segmentation separates free-flow or dense from congested regimes, permitting the investigation of
23 the impact of this control policy under each case of the aforementioned defined conditions. Lane-
24 related relationships are employed to better describe traffic behavior than the initial approach of
25 the kinematic/wave model (17), as was also shown at (18 – 20).

26 To promote the timely activation of the hard shoulder, short-term prediction models are
27 estimated per regime, namely for each segment, since driving behaviour is distinctively different.
28 Hence, the respective regime is better represented and the attained predictions' accuracy is
29 greater. The approach suggests that left lane's dense or bound flow denotes corresponding flow at
30 the right and shoulder lane, using as response variable the left lane flow distribution ratio
31 (LLFDR). The behavioral dimension is further modeled by assessing the satisfaction of the users
32 regarding the HSR system with ordered probit models, following a conducted survey.

33 The study is completed with an economic evaluation of the HSR for different trip
34 purposes. The costs and benefits of the control policy are quantified through an approximation of
35 travel time and consequent costs in terms of gasoline, maintenance etc.

36 37 **Traffic**

38 Piecewise parameterization is used in this study to provide a reasonable approach to the
39 underlying traffic behavioral relationships, so as to enhance interpretability. The piecewise
40 models are additive models, inheriting the properties of the linear models and increasing the
41 flexibility (21). They are described as follows (eq. 1):
42

$$E[Y|\vec{X} = \vec{x}] = a + \sum_{j=1}^p f_j(x_j) \quad (1)$$

1 where $f_j(x_j) = \beta_j x_j$ can be nonlinear function. In order to restrict each observation to affect the
 2 response variable proportionally, $E[Y] = a$ and $[f_j(x_j)] = 0$.

3 The returned segmented relationships provide the breakpoint between congested and
 4 uncongested conditions of the site.

5
 6 *Statistical Assessment of Forecasting Performance*

7
 8 The predictive performance of the models is assessed with the following statistical indices, in
 9 order to evaluate different aspects of the traffic parameters (1).

10 The normalized root mean square error (eq. 2) and root mean square percentage error (eq.
 11 3) penalize larger errors:

12
$$RMSN = \frac{\sqrt{N \sum_{n=1}^N (Y_n^S - Y_n^O)^2}}{\sum_{n=1}^N Y_n^O} \quad (2)$$

13
 14
$$RMSPE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \left(\frac{Y_n^S - Y_n^O}{Y_n^O} \right)^2} \quad (3)$$

15
 16 where Y_n^S are the predicted and Y_n^O are the observed values and N is the number of observations.

17
 18 **Behavioral**

19 *Ordered probit model*

20 Respondents in surveys are usually asked to express their preferences in ordered scale (16). A
 21 multinomial logit model could be estimated, with each response to be used as an alternative.
 22 However, this leads to simplification of the errors of the alternatives, because it violates their
 23 independence. However, the ordering of the alternatives violates the independence of the errors
 24 for each alternative, and therefore the Independence for Irrelevant Alternatives (IIA) assumption
 25 of the logit model. The ordered logit or probit models should be used instead, because apart from
 26 the coefficients of the explanatory variables, they estimate parameters for the intercepts between
 27 the alternative choices. Figure 1 shows the choice probability distribution as a function of the
 28 utility U. As in the case examined here, there are five ordered choices (“Not at all”, “Slightly”,
 29 “Moderately”, “Strongly”, “Very strongly”). Depending on the utility of the respondent, the
 30 equivalent choice is made. For instance, when the utility is less than k_1 “Not at all” is chosen,
 31 when the utility is between k_1 and k_2 “Slightly” is selected.

34 **FIGURE 1. Distribution of the respondents' preference (adapted from 22).**

In the case study, the answer of the respondent has been added directly as a dependent variable into the model. The response variable takes values from 1 to 5, with 1 indicating that the respondent is not at all satisfied by the Managed Lane system, and 5 indicating that he is highly satisfied.

If Y is the response factor with K levels, the model can be written as:

$$P(Y \leq k_j | x) = P(\beta'x \leq \theta_j) = P(u \leq \theta_j - \beta'x) = \Phi(\theta_j - \beta'x) \quad (4)$$

where:

- Φ is the cumulative normal function
- $\Phi(\theta_j - \beta'x)$ is the cumulative distribution function of an unobserved random error term u
- $\theta_0 = -\infty < \theta_1 < \dots < \theta_k = \infty$
- x is the vector of the explanatory factors, and
- β is the vector of the unknown parameters

ANALYSIS

Traffic

To optimize an HSR control system, its timely operation shall be assured before the maximum utilization of lanes is reached, in order to mitigate the aggravation of traffic conditions. Lane flow distribution relationships were employed to delineate the traffic dynamics, and the origin and magnitude of the traffic patterns during morning peak hours. As it was introduced in a previous study of the authors (1), the lane flow distribution ratio (LFDR) per lane is the ratio r_i , expressed in percentage, of the flow of each lane, Q_i , divided by the total flow of the direction, Q_{dir} , constrained by 0. The relationship between the LFDRs of each lane is as follows (eq. 5):

$$a_L \cdot r_L + a_R \cdot r_R + a_{HS} \cdot r_{HS} + \beta = 1$$

or

$$a_L \cdot \frac{Q_L}{Q_{dir}} + a_R \cdot \frac{Q_R}{Q_{dir}} + a_{HS} \cdot \frac{Q_{HS}}{Q_{dir}} + \beta = 1, \quad (5)$$

for

$$Q_{dir} = \sum_i Q_i \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$$

where a_i , β are the coefficients estimated by locally weighted regression, and i is left, right or hard shoulder lane. Moreover, to avoid misinterpretation of rapid fluctuations, a temporal aggregation of 3-min intervals was effectuated (1).

In Figure 2 for a value of flow $Q_L = 2360$ veh/h/lane at the fast-left lane and $Q_R = 2850$ veh/h/lane at the slow-right lane, LFDR is maximized. The two segments that are created before and after this breakpoint represent the uncongested or dense regimes and the congested conditions at the study area. In the second segment area, hysteretic phenomena are emerged in the form of high scatters for high values of flow that maximize LFDR at both regular lanes, before the system's activation that is depicted with blue points, indicating that lane's capacity has been reached. Hysteresis is more pronounced downstream, as observations (1) reveal that the phenomenon is present even in the hard shoulder.

(a) Fast lane

(b) Slow lane

1 **FIGURE 2: Segmentation of lane flow distribution ratio (LFDR) using piecewise linear**
2

1 Short-Term Prediction Models

2 In order to ameliorate the operation of a reactive ML system by forecasting driver's behavior and
 3 thus activate HSR shortly before the emergence of congested regimes, short-term prediction
 4 models were elaborated. The approach envisages employment of the lane-related parameter, left
 5 lane flow distribution ratio (LLFDR) as response variable, based on traffic stream observations
 6 where left lane's dense regimes signify likewise dense conditions at the right and HS lane.

7 Following the piecewise analysis, two models were developed before and after a
 8 breakpoint that depicts a significant change of traffic dynamics and categorizes the stream in
 9 congested and non-congested regime. The prediction intervals were set at 3-minutes and 9-
 10 minutes, a sufficient time period for forecasting the forthcoming traffic trends and adapt
 11 accordingly the disposable control policies. The estimated linear regression models are described
 12 with explanatory variables the current LLFDR, the LLFDR of 3 and 6-minutes prior to the current
 13 and the speed of the right and HS lanes.

14 For the uncongested segment of the stream consisted of 164 observations, the first model
 15 is described from the current LLFDR, X_{R_c} , the LLFDR of 3-min prior to the current, $X_{R_{c-3}}$, and
 16 the speed of the right lane, X_{V_2} , as shown in equation 6.

$$Y = \beta_{R_c} X_{R_c} + \beta_{R_{c-3}} X_{R_{c-3}} + \beta_{V_2} X_{V_2} \quad (6)$$

18 The estimated LLFDR is positively affected by the LLFDR 3-minuted prior to the current
 19 LLFDR and the latter. The speed of the right lane negatively affects the estimation, indicating that
 20 increased speed levels of the right lane and thus the lane's uncongested conditions lead to
 21 decreased occupancy of the left lane. Nevertheless, the variable of right's lane speed proved
 22 insignificant, and it was omitted from the model for the second segment of congested conditions.
 23 Based on the RMSN and RMSE, the predictions of the shorter interval were better than the
 24 longer, confirming relative literature.

26 The congested conditions (the second segment) were delineated with the explanatory
 27 variables of the current, 3 and 6-minutes prior to the current LLFDR, as well as the speed of the
 28 hard shoulder (eq. 7).

$$Y = \beta_{R_c} X_{R_c} + \beta_{R_{c-3}} X_{R_{c-3}} + \beta_{R_{c-6}} X_{R_{c-6}} + \beta_{V_3} X_{V_3} \quad (7)$$

30 Also for the congested conditions the LLFDR is positively affected by the
 31 aforementioned variables, but the speed of the hard shoulder, fortifying the presumption that
 32 when users are occupying the hard shoulder lane, the remaining lanes are less congested.
 33

34

1 **TABLE 1. Short-term left lane flow distribution (LLFDR) prediction models.**

Variables	Specification	Segment 1				Segment 2			
		$lm1_3$		$lm1_9$		$lm2_3$		$lm2_9$	
Lag (min)		3 (n=164)		9 (n=164)		3 (n=966)		9 (n=966)	
		Value	t-test	Value	t-test	Value	t-test	Value	t-test
Intercept		0.501	2.34	0.579	2.11	0.193	6.29	0.135	3.96
β_{R_c}	current LLFDR	0.542	2.34	0.342	3.70	0.386	3.18	0.413	9.02
$\beta_{R_{c-3}}$	LLFDR 3-min prior to current	0.258	3.99	0.320	3.43	0.158	8.03	0.113	2.14
$\beta_{R_{c-6}}$	LLFDR 6-min prior to current	-	-	-	-	0.085	1.66	0.070	1.67
β_{V_2}	current speed of right lane	-0.004	-2.09	-0.004	-1.70	-	-	-	-
β_{V_3}	current speed of hard shoulder	-	-	-	-	-0.0004	-4.58	-0.0002	-1.93
R²		0.60		0.43		0.55		0.53	
AIC		-418.23		-359.05		-1256.32		-1239.37	
Residual St. Error		0.07		0.08		0.05		0.04	
Validation tests									
RMSN		0.16		0.19		0.10		0.11	
RMSPE		0.18		0.20		0.11		0.11	

3

4 **Behavioral Model Development**

5 In total 584 questionnaires were collected. Despite the efforts for random data collection, an
6 uneven split between gender and age was observed, indicating that the ratio of the number of
7 men-to-women who use the freeway is approximately 2:1. From the entire sample, 71% declared
8 that they strongly or very strongly agree that traffic conditions have been ameliorated after the
9 implementation of the system. The 13% of the respondents expressed strong and 65% enough
10 satisfaction following the policy. Furthermore, the safety level was stated to be maintained or
11 improved, thus the absence of the hard shoulder lane during peak hours that the system is
12 activated and the VSL enforcement was not only disturbing, but even appreciated.

13 Regarding the frequency of the system's use, 71% of the respondents have used the
14 system at least once. Furthermore, 23% commute within the segment several times per week and
15 15% on a daily basis. Based on the total number of responses, only 25% declared inconvenience
16 to cross the white continuous line (5% not at all convenient, 20% slightly inconvenient), versus
17 71% (59% very strongly convenient, 12% strongly convenient). Respectively, 19% of frequent
18 users were concerned in crossing the line (2% very strongly concerned, 17% strongly concerned),
19 versus 79% that entered in the emergency lane while it was activated (69% not at all concerned,
20 10% slightly concerned). The above findings are presented in Figures 3-4.

21

(a) Âge

(b) Sexe

(c) Ligne continue gênante

(d) Sécurité

(a) Utilisation de la BAU lorsque ouverte

(b) Amélioration de la sécurité

(c) Amélioration de la fluidité du trafic

(d) Satisfaction par le système

FIGURE 4. Summary statistics

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Based on the information provided by the respondents, the adaptation of the users to the system was analyzed by the models that were developed. This was approached by a parameterization of their satisfaction through an ordered probit model. The results denote that drivers less than 30 years old are more satisfied by the system. The users' satisfaction decreases as their inconvenience to cross the white continuous line increases. Moreover, the higher the improvement of the level of traffic conditions and safety is perceived to be, accordingly greater is their level of satisfaction. Thus, younger drivers are more adapted to the HSR system, as they are less hesitant to cross the white line that separates the regular lanes from the HS, without being more disturbed or insecure by the absence of an emergency lane in the freeway. Drivers that use HS several times per week or daily are more satisfied. Following the ordered logit model estimation for both men and

1 women, we attempted to investigate whether there is a systematic difference in behavior based on
 2 gender.

3 **TABLE 2: Satisfaction model**
 4

Name	Specification	All N=451		Female N=145		Male N=306	
		Estimates	t-test	Estimates	t-test	Estimates	t-test
X_{age}	Age > 30	-0.393	-2.47	-0.109	-0.42	-0.66	-3.20
X_{sec}	Security	0.528	7.53	0.55	4.24	0.548	6.29
X_{flow}	Traffic conditions	0.706	9.83	0.592	4.51	0.768	8.62
X_{whl}	White line	-0.156	-3.56	-0.115	-1.61	-0.161	-2.83
X_{ut}	Frequent use (several times per week and daily basis)	0.323	2.671	0.542	2.526	0.201	1.34
X_{oc}	HS open	0.258	1.931	0.15	0.640	0.373	2.27
Intercepts							
1 2		0.935	2.76	1.156	2.01	0.813	1.88
2 3		1.98	6.06	2.125	3.80	1.939	4.71
3 4		2.774	8.276	2.953	5.127	2.729	6.48
4 5		5.40	13.85	5.431	8.07	5.498	11.11
AIC		747.98		270.42		487.04	
Residual deviance		727.98		250.42		467.04	
Log-likelihood		-363.9921		-125.211		-233.5209	

5
 6
 7 In order to assess if the predicted values by the model using all the observations are significantly
 8 different than those predicted by the individual models, a likelihood ratio test has been applied
 9 (23). In this test, the restricted model is that the coefficients between the two models are the same,
 10 while the unrestricted model is one in different models should be estimated for the male vs.
 11 female data sets.

12
 13 Restricted: -363.99
 14 Unrestricted: -125.211 – 233.5209 = -358.7319
 15 LL test = -2 * (-363.99 – (-358.7319)) = -10.52

16
 17 The degrees of freedom for the chi square test are equal to 10 (i.e. the number of additional
 18 parameters that are estimated in the case of the restricted model). The p-value obtained from the
 19 chi square test with a value equal to -10.52 and 10 degrees of freedom is equal to 1 suggesting
 20 that the null hypothesis is not rejected. Therefore, it can be concluded that the gender does not
 21 have a significant impact in the model results. Moreover, a random effects model has been
 22 applied, resulting in insignificant sigma, validating verifying that the selection of the above model
 23 is appropriate. Figure 5 shows the estimated coefficients and standard errors of the models.

FIGURE 5. Model comparison
Blue: Males, Red: Females, Orange: All

Travel time analysis

Another aspect of measuring the efficiency is the amelioration of the travel time on the road section that is equipped with the system. Using the travel times, the costs and benefits are being measured and translated to advantages and disadvantages for the society. For this analysis, aggregate data of 30 seconds intervals have been used. Since traffic data before the implementation of the system were not available, this situation can be approximately represented by data collected during a period that the system was inactive, from 13 to 17 of December 2010, when the traffic was limited to the two lanes.

The travel time between Morges-Est end Ecublens can be approximated by:

$$tt = \frac{km_j - km_i}{\bar{v}_j - \bar{v}_i} \quad (8)$$

$$Q = \sum_{lanes} \bar{k}_i \cdot \bar{v}_i \quad (9)$$

$$tt_{total} = \sum_{HS\ open} tt \cdot Q \quad (10)$$

where tt is the travel time, km_j is the position j of a vehicle fleet that is after the position i , $\bar{v}_{i,j}$ is the average speed of the fleet at position i or j , Q is the flow for the number of lanes that are used

1 at a given time (2 or 3 lanes according to the HSR system status), and tt_{total} is the total travel
 2 time that vehicles travelled while the system was active.

3 The generalized travel cost takes into account the time cost, the vehicle operating costs
 4 (gasoline, maintenance, purchase etc.), the taxes, tolls and comfort based on the Swiss standards
 5 (24). In this analysis the following assumptions have been made:

- 6 • The vehicular costs before and after the implementation of the systems are the same
- 7 • The taxes between 2008 and 2010 are the same
- 8 • The Swiss highway toll between 2008 and 2010 is the same
- 9 • The variability of the travel time is the same before and after the introduction of the
 10 system
- 11 • There amount is a proxy of the net Present Value, since the data are coming from the
 12 same year

13
 14 Different value of travel time estimates by different trip purposes and modes for
 15 Switzerland are presented in Table 3.

16 **TABLE 3. Value of time in Switzerland (25)**

Trip purpose	Private transport with motorized vehicles (CHF/h)
All purposes	23.29
Work	31.45
Shopping	20.72
Commercial	32.24
Touristic	22.05

17
 18 The social benefits are computed by the following function (24, 25):

$$19 \quad \text{Benefits/Costs} = \sum_{HS \text{ open}} \text{value of time} \cdot \Delta \text{time of route}_{30s} \cdot \text{cost}_{30s} \quad (11)$$

20 In order to quantify the benefits and costs of the HSR, a period that the system was operational
 21 (22/11/2010-10/12/2010) was compared to a week that the temporary hard shoulder use was
 22 suspended (13-17/12/2010). The most representative days, according to previous traffic analysis
 23 (1), are Tuesday and Thursday for the commuter traffic, and Friday for the weekend traffic. Based
 24 on eq. 11 and Table 3, the traffic is multiplied by a different cost-coefficient when the observation
 25 day was a weekday, so the trip purpose is for work, and another for the weekend, when are
 26 multiple purposes. The results are presented per peak hour periods as difference of costs or
 27 benefits between the operational and suspended periods in Table 4, and as percentages Table 5
 28 only for the two regular lanes, even when HSR is activated, or only for the hard shoulder, for
 29 scaling comparison purposes.

1 **TABLE 4. Difference of costs (in red) and benefits (in green) of HSR system per day during**
 2 **operational (22/11/2010-10/12/2010) and suspended (13-17/12/2010) periods.**

Price in CHF	Direction Lausanne	
	Morning peak hour	Night peak hour
<i>Commuter traffic (31.45 CHF/h)</i>		
Tuesday 30 November and 14 December	2,249.64	3,607.65
Tuesday 7 and 14 December	2,922.40	2,376.81
Thursday 25 November and 2 December	55.31	6,613.67
Thursday 2 and 9 December	-744.64	4,281.53
Thursday 9 and 16 December	1,942.71	4,282.51
<i>Week-end traffic(31.45 CHF/h morning, 23.29 CHF/h evening)</i>		
Friday 25 November and 3 December	1,816.50	5,985.01
Friday 3 and 10 December	1,525.92	2,892.27
Friday 10 and 17 December	605.25	872.68
Total gains	37%	55%
Gains from HS	13%	11%

3

4 **TABLE 5. Percentage Costs (in red) and Benefits (in green) of HSR system per day during**
 5 **operational (22/11/2010-10/12/2010) and suspended (13-17/12/2010) periods.**

	Total gains		Gains from HS	
	Morning peak	Night peak	Morning peak	Night peak
Tuesday 30 November and 14 December	37%	55%	13%	11%
Tuesday 7 and 14 December	44%	58%	17%	13%
Thursday 25 November and 2 December	-5%	58%	4%	20%
Thursday 2 and 9 December	-9%	50%	-4%	10%
Thursday 9 and 16 December	39%	49%	11%	11%
Friday 25 November and 3 December	33%	56%	18%	19%
Friday 3 and 10 December	26%	47%	12%	6%
Friday 10 and 17 December	2%	44%	8%	-1%

6

7

8 CONCLUSIONS

9 The objective of this research is to investigate the amelioration of the traffic conditions of a
 10 highway segment equipped with a hard shoulder running system by performing a multi-
 11 dimensional analysis. To optimize the operation of this increasingly used ITS strategy, namely
 12 activating the system before the maximum capacity is reached, three aspects are examined: traffic,
 13 behavioral and econometric.

14 For the traffic analysis a segmentation of the observations is applied with piecewise
 15 models on the lane distribution ratio, using 3-minutes aggregated traffic data collected from radar
 16 sensors along the freeway. The aim of this analysis is to identify the flow and LFDR values where
 17 the traffic conditions change significantly. Two segments were resulted representing the free-flow
 18 or dense conditions and the congested. In the lane flow distribution relationships that were
 19 studied, an underutilization of the system was delineated, as the HSR was activated only after

1 high scatters of flow that maximized LFDR were emerged, thus hysteretic phenomena, and
2 congested regimes were pronounced. The purpose of this segmentation is to estimate short-term
3 prediction models per segment, attaining higher accuracy. The estimated models use as response
4 variable the LLFDR, a methodology that has been introduced by Samoili et al. (1). Different
5 models were formed for 3 and 9 minutes prediction horizon with significant prediction
6 estimations and low prediction uncertainties that strengthen for the longer horizons.

7 The behavior of the users of a managed lane system is modeled to assess the policy and
8 address accordingly any adjustments, so as to ameliorate the traffic conditions of the highway
9 segment in question (A1). An on-site survey was conducted and 584 questionnaires were
10 collected. Ordered probit models are developed with the satisfaction of the users about the HSR
11 system scaled from 1 to 5 as response variable and significant conclusions can be drawn. Three
12 satisfaction models are estimated: one for the whole sample, and others for men and women
13 subsets. The results show that young drivers up to 30 years old and frequent drivers are more
14 satisfied than the others. The more satisfied users perceive that the system offers more security,
15 the traffic conditions have been ameliorated, while they are annoyed by the continuous white line.
16 The market segmentation analysis by estimating two different models for males and females
17 shows that this information does not have a significant impact in the results of the models. The
18 last part of this multi-perspective analysis includes an economic assessment of the system. The
19 results clearly show a total economic benefit from the system's usage.
20

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25

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